

MARCS: MACHINE LEARNING FOR SEISMIC PERFORMANCE PREDICTION OF RC BUILDINGS ON SLOPES

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Abstract: *Recently, hilly areas in India have seen an unprecedented rise in construction activities due to increased human and economic activities. One of the most common types of buildings being constructed on slopes are RC step-back buildings. The seismic performance of the buildings is a function of the properties of construction materials and the structure's geometry, which is governed by the topography of the construction site. Evaluating the seismic performance of buildings with similar structures but different material properties requires performing computationally expensive nonlinear dynamic analyses. In this work, we consider the uncertainty in concrete and steel material properties to create a large database of 4-story RC buildings in hilly terrain. Further, the seismic performance of these buildings is obtained through nonlinear dynamic analyses using OpenSeesPy. The generated dataset is then used to train a machine learning model that can generate the fragility curve parameters for the considered building by taking input of the material properties, fundamental period, and targeted limit state. The advantage of such a machine learning model is that it eliminates the need for computationally expensive nonlinear dynamic analyses to obtain the seismic performance of the buildings. The framework proposed in this study demonstrates how machine learning can accelerate seismic performance prediction of sloped RC buildings by accounting for material uncertainties.*

1 Introduction

The construction activities have significantly increased due to the rise in economic and human activities in hilly areas. The recent surveys conducted by researchers in cities situated in the Himalayas of India and Nepal observed that even after using reinforced concrete (RC) for construction buildings on sloped surfaces, they have incurred significant damage during seismic activities (Aggarwal and Saha (2021); Sharma et al. (2012); Surana et al. (2018b); Varum et al. (2018)). From the detailed field surveys conducted in Mussoorie and Nainital (Uttarakhand) by Surana et al. (2018b), Dehradun (Uttarakhand) by Lang et al. (2012), Gangtok (Sikkim) by Sharma et al. (2012), and in Mandi (Himachal Pradesh) by Aggarwal and Saha (2023) revealed that step-back buildings are at severe risk of damage due to earthquakes. This is because of the uneven distribution of mass, stiffness, and strength in these types of buildings, as revealed by Surana et al. (2018b). Despite being absence of codal provision for the seismic design of buildings on slopes, several studies have already been conducted to assess the seismic performance of these buildings.

Surana et al. (2018c) compared the seismic performance of 4-storey buildings under flat land, split foundation, and step-back configuration. They concluded that the collapse occurred in buildings on flat land due to flexural

failure of structural elements. In contrast, in buildings on the slope, the combined effect of shear failure of short columns and flexural failure of structural elements governed the failure. In another study, Surana et al. (2020) reported that seismic demand estimation using PGA as intensity measure (IM) results in overestimating the mean damage ratio compared to when spectral acceleration-based intensity measures are used for sloped buildings. Further, researchers studied the seismic performance of different building typologies in Indian hilly regions. The authors compared the effect of slope angle on seismic performance and observed that with an increase in slope angle, the probability of shear failure increases, making it the dominant mode of failure in buildings situated on steep slopes (Patil and Raghunandan (2021)). The researchers have also studied the effect of open ground story on the collapse performance of sloped buildings during seismic activities (Aggarwal and Saha (2021)). The authors found that the presence of an open storey above ground level leads to more risk to the seismic safety of the building as compared to the case when it is present at the storey below ground level. From past studies, it is evident that nonlinear dynamic analysis-based methods are crucial yet computationally intensive for evaluating the seismic performance of the structures.

With the development of computational hardware and algorithms, machine learning (ML) became one of the promising techniques to overcome the limitations of existing methods for seismic performance assessment of buildings. Recently, Hwang et al. (2021) proposed a methodology for predicting the seismic response and structural collapse of two ductile RC frames by considering the components and system-level modelling uncertainties. They observed that the effect of structural uncertainties on seismic requirements is reasonably negligible, up to moderate levels of structural damage. Kiani et al. (2019) trained a classification machine learning model by considering the ground motion characteristics as input features to predict the fragility curves and structural response of an 8-storey steel moment resisting frame. The authors observed that the tree-based model best predicts the fragility curves. In another work, Wu and Di Sarno (2023) proposed a feed-forward neural network (FNN) method to predict the exceedance of the given limit state for masonry-infilled steel frames. The authors observed that this method requires significantly fewer computational resources than the traditional Incremental Dynamic Analysis (IDA) for obtaining fragility curves with similar accuracy. Kazemi et al. (2023) studied the effect of geometrical properties and the fundamental period of buildings, along with spectral acceleration at the fundamental period, to predict the seismic response of RC buildings. Based on previous studies, it is observed that researchers have investigated RC bare frames, masonry infilled frames, steel buildings, and building elements using ML to obtain their seismic performance.

Figure 1. Framework to develop ML models for predicting fragility curve parameters

As shown in the brief methodology adopted in this work (Figure 1), we considered the finite element model of a sloped 4-storey building with varying material properties obtained using the Latin Hypercube Sampling method. The buildings with different material properties are subjected to nonlinear dynamic analyses using a ground motion suite comprising 184 ground motions to determine fragility curve parameters at different limit states. Machine learning models were then trained to predict fragility curve parameters by considering the material properties of the building, fundamental period, and limit states as input features. The present paper

is organized as follows: first, we discuss how the building is modelled in *OpenSeesPy* (Zhu et al. (2018)) followed by generating material properties using LHS. Then, we discuss the ground motions used for performing non-linear dynamic analysis. This is followed by a brief description of the machine learning model, dataset preparation, and model training protocol adopted in this work. Finally, we discuss how fragility parameters are obtained using ML and compare them with the fragility curves obtained through nonlinear dynamic analyses. We then conclude by discussing the key findings and limitations of this work, followed by recommendations on future research directions.

2 Methodology

2.1 Modelling of 4-storey RC building on slope

In this work, a 4-storey sloped building is taken into consideration as an example of the Indian residential/commercial building typology. The building has three spans of 3.2 m each, a uniform storey height of 3.3 m, and a slope angle of 27.3 degrees, as recommended by Jain and Surana (2022). The elevation of the modelled building is shown in Figure 2. The dead load of 23kN/m and the live load of 6.25kN/m are considered during the modelling, analysis, and design. The frames are made in accordance with the Indian standards, IS 456 (2021), IS 1893 : Part 1 (2016), and IS 13920 (2016), for soil type I and Indian seismic zone V (PGA=0.36g). The size of the first short column (near ground level) is 900 mm x 900 mm, while the other short column has cross-section dimensions of 500 mm x 500 mm. All other columns are of the size 350 mm x 350 mm. The cross-section of beams in the building is 300 mm x 400 mm. The column reinforcement ranges from 1.5 to 3%, while beam reinforcement ranges from 0.75 to 1.5 %. The building investigated in this work is modelled using *OpenSeesPy* (Zhu et al. (2018)).

Figure 2. Elevation of the 4-Storey building frame

The concrete (both confined and unconfined) and steel rebars are numerically modelled by using "*Concrete02*" and "*Steel02*," respectively. The concrete model parameters are derived from the Modified Kent and Park model. The tension softening stiffness (E_t) for the "*Concrete02*" material is expressed as a function of the tensile strength of concrete (f_t) through the expression $f_t/0.002$. To generate 200 sets of material properties, data on the distribution and coefficient of variations (COVs) for unconfined concrete strength and strain are

sourced from existing literature Zheng et al. (2022). The “Steel02” material model is based on the Giuffre-Menegotto-Pinto model and accounts for Bauschinger's effect resulting from dynamic loading in the reinforcement steel rebars reported by Filippou et al. (1983). The distribution and COVs for input parameters of the “Steel02” model are obtained from the experimentally validated research reported by Carreño et al. (2020). The “fiber” section-based “forceBeamColumn” element is used for modelling beams and columns with the “GaussLobatto” integrator and five integration points distributed along the element's length (Scott and Fenves (2006)). Since the building is situated on a sloped surface, the length of columns at the base differs from those above ground level. Also, the columns below ground level are more susceptible to shear failure than those above ground level, which experience both shear and flexural failure. Hence, “zeroLength” element in *OpenSeesPy* is used to model shear and flexural spring in the base columns to incorporate different failure modes. The shear limit curve proposed by Elwood and Moehle (2003) is considered to model the shear spring at the ends of the base columns.

2.2 Material properties selection and sampling

The previous research by Barbato et al. (2010); Carreño et al. (2020); Jr et al. (2022); Latif et al. (2022); Surana et al. (2022), (2018a); Zheng et al. (2022) demonstrated that the construction materials exhibit significant variability, and diverse construction practices introduce uncertainties in structural responses. Furthermore, to achieve precise modelling of buildings, it is essential to appropriately calibrate material models, as Rayjada et al. (2023) suggested. Regarding concrete, Jr et al. (2022) highlight the substantial impact of parameters such as peak compressive strength (f_{cu}), strain (ϵ_{cu}), steel's yield strength (f_y), elastic modulus (E), post-yield strain hardening ratio (b), and the curvature variation parameter of the Bauschinger curve after each strain reversal (cR_1) on the seismic behaviour of reinforced concrete (RC) elements.

Table 1. Mean and coefficient of variation of material properties

Materials	Properties	Mean	COV (%)
Concrete	f_{cu} (MPa)	38.56	20
	ϵ_{cu}	0.002	20
Steel	f_y (MPa)	518	4.2
	E (GPa)	212	1.6
	b	0.019	9.6
	cR_1	0.891	0.6

To generate 200 sets of material properties for studying the effect of material uncertainties on the seismic performance of sloped buildings, the properties of concrete from Barbato et al. (2010); Zheng et al. (2022), and steel properties from Carreño et al. (2020) used in this work are listed in Table 1. Latin hypercube sampling generates the samples using six material modelling parameters, their respective mean, coefficient of variations (COV), and distributions. All the material properties follow the lognormal distribution except E and cR_1 which follows the normal distribution as seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The distribution of the input material properties obtained using LHS (a) f_{cu} , (b) ϵ_{cu} , (c) f_y , (d) E , (e) b , (f) cR_1

2.3 Ground motion selection

To perform nonlinear dynamic analysis and derive parameters for fragility curves that accurately represent site-specific earthquake hazards, it is essential to have an appropriate collection of ground motions. In this study, we've considered a set of 184 ground motions with pulse-like characteristics, as originally suggested by Kohrangi et al. (2019). The distribution of magnitude and hypocentral distance of these ground motions is depicted in Figure 4. The selected ground motions have moment magnitudes ranging from 5.0 to 7.6, with an average of 6.79. Also, the larger number of points in the top left corner of Figure 4 indicates the dataset has severe ground motions with high moment magnitude and shorter hypocentral distance, implying their severity. Furthermore, the peak ground acceleration associated with these ground motions varies from 0.05g to 1.3g, with an average value of 0.34g.

Figure 4. Distribution of magnitude and hypocentral distance of the considered ground motions.

2.4 Nonlinear dynamic analysis

Nonlinear dynamic analysis assesses a building's seismic performance by subjecting the finite element model of the building to scaled ground motions. Further, it requires appropriate intensity measures (IM) and engineering demand parameters (EDP) to quantify this performance. In this work, we have selected PGA and inter-storey drift ratio, which are widely used IM and EDP, respectively. After the analysis, fragility curve parameters are obtained at various limit states by postprocessing the results of nonlinear dynamic analysis. Mathematically, according to Eq. (1), fragility analysis measures the probability (P_f) of an engineering demand parameter exceeding a set threshold for a specific intensity measure (IM).

$$P_f(ds \geq dsi | IM_i) = \Phi \left(\frac{\ln(IM_i/\theta)}{\beta_T} \right) \quad (1)$$

Here, Φ represents the standard normal cumulative distribution function (CDF), and IM_i stands for the intensity measure of interest. It is used to calculate the desired P_f at a given EDP threshold, denoted as dsi , with θ representing the median IM value. β_T quantifies the fragility analysis uncertainty and is defined as the square root of the sum of squared contributions from record-to-record variability and modelling uncertainty. In this study, we consider three different limit states: Immediate Occupancy (IO), Life Safety (LS), and Collapse Prevention (CP), each corresponding to inter-story drift limits of 1%, 2%, and 4%, respectively, as recommended by FEMA 450 (Part 1) (2003).

2.5 Machine learning for predicting fragility curve parameters

The dataset for training the ML algorithm for predicting fragility curve parameters, i.e., θ and β , is obtained from non-linear dynamic analysis. Specifically, the model considers the input of six material properties, the fundamental period of the buildings, and the limit state and gives the output of corresponding fragility curve parameters. The dataset is then split into training and test ratios of 80% and 20%, respectively. Further, k -fold cross-validation with $k=4$ is applied to the training data, thus yielding an effective train, validation, and test split of 60:20:20. The model performing best on the validation set is used to obtain predictions on the test set, which is kept completely hidden during the training procedure. Note that separate models are trained for predicting θ and β , using the same methodology described in this section.

Figure 5. Schematic of XGBoost model

Considering the success of tree-based models from the research literature, the XGBoost model is used in the work to predict the fragility curve parameters. Figure 5 shows a brief schematic of the XGBoost model, which

takes input data, and then the number of trees is increased till the specified limit. Each tree is created to minimize the error made by the preceding ensemble of trees. XGBoost is a tree-boosting machine learning model which uses K additive trees for predicting the target variables, as mentioned in Eq. (2), where $\phi(x_i)$ is the model prediction for i^{th} input, x_i is the respective input vector, and f_k is the individual regression tree, \mathcal{F} is the collection of all regression trees. A detailed description of the ML models can be found in Chen and Guestrin (2016), the work that introduced this algorithm. To evaluate the performance of trained machine learning models, metrics like coefficient of determination, root mean squared error, and mean absolute error are used. The mathematical expression of these coefficients is listed in Table 2.

$$\hat{y}_i = \phi(x_i) = \sum_{k=1}^K f_k(x_i), f_k \in \mathcal{F} \quad (2)$$

Table 2. Different error metrics used in the present study

Metrics	Equations
Coefficient of determination (R2)	$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y'_i - y_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y'_i - \bar{y})^2}$
Root mean square error (RMSE)	$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y'_i - y_i)^2}{n}}$
Mean absolute error (MAE)	$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y'_i - y_i $

Note: y = actual value, y' = predicted value, \bar{y} = mean of actual values, n = number of data points.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Fragility analysis

Considering the uncertainty in different material properties, the distribution of a fundamental period (Figure 6) of a 4-storey sloped building varies from 0.34 s to 0.67 s, indicating a wide variety of buildings in the dataset. The distribution is also subjected to the Anderson-Darling test to identify whether it follows a lognormal distribution. The p-value of the test was 0.4, which is higher than 0.05, indicating that the hypothesis of considering fundamental distribution as lognormal holds good. On comparing the fundamental period of 200 buildings with IS-1893, it was observed that 123 buildings have fundamental period values less than the values recommended by the IS code. Further, for 77 buildings, the codal provision underpredicted the fundamental period. This is because codal provision do not account for material and geometric properties of the buildings.

Figure 6. Visualizing distribution of fundamental period of 4-storey sloped buildings

Following the approach suggested by Baker (2015), the buildings generated using LHS were subjected to nonlinear dynamic analysis using a suite of 184 ground motions to get the fragility curve parameters for three limit states of IO, LS, and CP. Figure 7 illustrates the distribution of the fragility curve parameters, median (θ), and standard deviation (β) for all the buildings using PGA as IM. From Figures 7(a) and 7(b), it is observed that the maximum number of buildings have θ values close to 0.125 and 0.19, respectively. However, Figure 7(c) shows that maximum buildings have θ close to 0.49 in collapse limit state. Further, θ in CP limit state is ~1.5 to 4 times the θ in IO and LS limit states respectively. This dispersion in fragility curve parameters can be explained due to wide range of material properties considered in this work to model the 4-storey sloped building. Since change in material properties leads to changes in seismic performance of the building, there exists the need of obtaining fragility curve parameters for new sets of input in an accurate and faster way. In this work, we attempt to insatiate this need using ML models by considering an example of 4-storey sloped building.

Figure 7. Visualizing distribution of fragility curve parameters of a 4-storey at different limit states (a) θ at IO limit state, (b) θ at LS limit state, (c) θ at CP limit state, (d) β at IO limit state (e) β at LS limit state, (f) β at CP limit state

3.2 ML for predicting fragility curve parameters

Table 3 shows the performance of the trained XGBoost models at predicting fragility curve parameters, which consider the input of material properties, fundamental period, and limit state of the building. When the performance of XGBoost models is evaluated based on R^2 scores, it is observed that the score of 0.99 and 0.90 is obtained for θ and β , respectively, on the test set, implying a good fit. Further, the RMSE and MAE values showing model performance in predicting θ and β indicate that the predicted values are quite accurate up to at least one place after decimal, again indicating the model's generalizability for different values of material properties.

Table 3. Performance of XGBoost model in predicting fragility curve parameters

Parameter	R^2		RMSE		MAE	
	Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test
θ	0.99	0.99	0.024	0.122	0.012	0.014
β	0.92	0.90	0.033	0.040	0.049	0.057

The hyperparameters ($n_estimators$, i.e., number of gradient-boosted trees and max_depth , i.e., the depth of trees) of trained models for predicting θ and β are listed in Table 4. The accumulation of points near the $y = x$ line in Figures 8 (a) and 8 (b) also implies the goodness of the fit of models trained for predicting the fragility curve parameters. It was observed from the distribution of θ values that in the CP limit state, they are 1.5 to 4 times higher than the median failure probability in IO and LS. Further, the distribution of θ values for each limit state are quite distinct (Figure 7 (a-c)). This phenomenon is also visible in Figure 8 (a), and the machine learning model correctly captured this trend. The median fragility curves obtained using nonlinear dynamic analyses and machine learning are compared in Figure 9.

Table 4. Hyperparameters of trained XGBoost models for predicting fragility curve parameters

Parameter	$n_estimators$	max_depth
θ	20	4
β	9	4

Figure 8. Performance of XGBoost Model for predicting fragility curves parameters (a) θ , (b) β

Figure 9 (a) shows the actual fragility curves where the solid lines of green, black, and red colour correspond to the curves at IO, LS, and CP limit states. The shaded area around each line represents the 5th to 95th percentile regions in which respective actual fragility curves exist. It should be noted that this shaded area occurs due to change in fragility curve parameters due to change in material properties. Similarly, Figure 9 (b) represents the same information for predicted fragility curves with dotted lines. To compare the actual and predicted fragility curves, the median curves shown in Figures 9 (a) and 9 (b) are plotted together in Figure 9 (c). It can be observed that both actual and predicted curves are quite close to each other in all the limit states, which is also reflected in Table 3, where the performance of ML models in predicting the fragility curve parameter is reported.

Figure 9. Comparing the actual and predicted fragility curves

4 Conclusion

This work considers the effect of material uncertainties on the seismic performance of RC buildings on slopes. Specifically, fragility analysis has been performed by considering PGA as the intensity measure and interstorey drift as the engineering demand parameter when the building is subjected to a suite of 184 ground motions. The six material properties considered uncertain are peak compressive strength and strain of unconfined concrete, and elastic modulus, post-yield strain hardening ratio, and the curvature variation parameter governing the response of reinforcement steel. The Latin hypercube sampling algorithm obtains 200 sets of material properties by considering their mean and coefficient of variations, thus providing 200 buildings subjected to nonlinear dynamic analyses for deriving their respective fragility curve parameters. The fundamental period of the generated buildings followed the lognormal distribution, as revealed through

Anderson-Darling statistical testing. Further, the IS-1893 codal provision underpredicted and overpredicted the fundamental period of 77 and 123 buildings, respectively. It is also observed that median collapse probability, i.e., θ values in the collapse limit state, are quite higher than IO and LS limit states. Also, the β values are highest in CP limit states. Further, machine learning is applied to predict the fragility curve parameters of a 4-storey sloped building as a function of its material properties and fundamental period. The application of machine learning proves that trained XGBoost models can be used to predict the fragility curve parameters accurately and quickly for buildings with different material properties without the need for time-consuming and complex nonlinear dynamic analysis. Since buildings can have varying slope angles and typologies in addition to variation in material properties depending upon geographical and geological conditions, there is a need to develop generalized machine learning models that can also consider slope angle variations, building typology, and structural uncertainties. Further, researchers can also gain insights into how each input parameter governs the seismic performance of buildings by using model explanation methods.

5 References

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